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4 **physiology and intellectual disability**

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36 **ABSTRACT**

37 Post-translational modifications (PTMs) represent a dynamic regulatory system that precisely modulates the
38 functional organization of synapses. PTMs consist in target modifications by small chemical moieties or
39 conjugation of lipids, sugars or polypeptides. Among them, ubiquitin and a large family of ubiquitin-like
40 proteins (UBLs) share several features such as the structure of the small protein modifiers, the enzymatic
41 cascades mediating the conjugation process and the targeted aminoacidic residue. In the brain, ubiquitination
42 and two UBLs, namely sumoylation and the recently discovered neddylation orchestrate fundamental
43 processes including synapse formation, maturation and plasticity, and their alteration is thought to contribute
44 to the development of neurological disorders. Remarkably, emerging evidence suggests that these pathways
45 tightly interplay to modulate the function of several proteins that possess pivotal roles for brain homeostasis as
46 well as failure of this crosstalk seems to be implicated in the development of brain pathologies. In this review,
47 we outline the role of ubiquitination, sumoylation, neddylation and their functional interplay in synapse
48 physiology and discuss their implication in the molecular pathogenesis of Intellectual Disability (ID), a
49 neurodevelopmental disorder that is frequently co-morbid with a wide spectrum of brain pathologies. Finally,
50 we propose a few outlooks that might contribute to better understand the complexity of these regulatory
51 systems in regard to neuronal circuit pathophysiology.

52

53 **SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT**

54 Ubiquitination, sumoylation and neddylation are related PTMs modulating cellular and molecular pathways
55 that are essential to generate fully functional neuronal circuits. Their impairment is indeed implicated in the
56 pathogenesis of several disorders, including ID. Growing evidence now indicates they also functionally
57 cooperate to govern synapse development and function. The main goals of this review are *(i)* to provide an
58 overview of the current knowledge on the role of ubiquitination, sumoylation and neddylation in synapse
59 functions; *(ii)* discuss how altered ubiquitination or sumoylation pathways may contribute to ID development;
60 *(iii)* highlight evidence of a dynamic crosstalk between these PTMs, which represent a novel mechanism that
61 could lead to the identification of new principles underlying synaptic function and dysfunction in ID.

62

63 INTRODUCTION

64 Synapses are the basic functional units of the brain ensuring proper information processing and storage. In the
65 forebrain, glutamate and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) are the main excitatory and inhibitory neurotransmitters
66 (NT), respectively. Synaptic transmission occurs when an action potential reaches the active zone of the
67 presynaptic terminal and triggers the Ca^{2+} -dependent fusion of synaptic vesicles (SVs) to the presynaptic
68 membrane (Südhof, 2004). SV fusion releases NT molecules into the synaptic cleft and convey a signal to NT
69 receptors localized in the membrane of a specialized domain of the postsynaptic neuron, called the
70 postsynaptic density (PSD). The PSD is composed by a complex network of distinct protein categories.
71 Among them, postsynaptic NT receptors transduce the signal conveyed by NTs into electrical and biochemical
72 cascades. Underneath the postsynaptic membrane, a meshwork of scaffolding proteins generates a structural
73 platform governing synapse organization via multiple bindings to NT receptors, adhesion proteins, signaling
74 molecules and cytoskeletal elements (Sheng and Kim, 2011).

75 A prominent feature of synapses is their ability to dynamically modify the strength of synaptic transmission
76 according to the inputs they receive, in a process called synaptic plasticity. Synaptic plasticity is thought to
77 underlie learning and memory and is fundamental to adapt our behavior based on experience. During brain
78 development, synaptic plasticity peaks in specific temporal windows of high sensitivity, called critical periods
79 (Hensch, 2005), which are crucial to orchestrate the formation and refinement of synaptic networks and,
80 ultimately, enables the acquisition of a given skill and/or cognitive function. The drawback of this particularly
81 high sensitivity is a marked susceptibility to genetic and environmental insults that can interfere with
82 molecular and cellular processes critical to synapse development, function and plasticity. Indeed, perturbation
83 of these pathways leads to neurodevelopmental and psychiatric disorders, such as autism, intellectual disability
84 (ID) and schizophrenia. Since these pathologies are characterized by the convergence of distinct pathways
85 onto synaptic impairment, they are collectively defined as synaptopathies (Van Spronsen and Hoogenraad,
86 2010). To date, no effective therapies are available to treat these diseases. It is therefore crucial to understand
87 the molecular mechanisms of synaptic dysfunction to provide the rationale to develop innovative therapeutic
88 approaches.

89 Given the plastic nature of the brain, synapses have developed strategies to rapidly modify the strength of
90 synaptic transmission. The dynamic modulation of protein activity via post-translational modifications (PTMs)
91 is a major mechanism to efficiently tune synapse assembly, maturation and function. PTMs refer to covalent
92 enzymatic modifications, either reversible or irreversible of target proteins, following their translation (Bürkle,
93 2001). They typically consist in the addition of a functional moiety, which can be either chemical groups or
94 complex molecules, including lipids, sugars, nucleosides and polypeptides to specific residues of target
95 proteins. PTMs regulate multiple aspects of protein physiology from subcellular localization and activity to
96 conformation and stability/turnover. In neurons, PTMs have been extensively investigated and modulate
97 virtually all pathways that are required to ensure proper synaptic transmission and plasticity, such as
98 presynaptic NT release (Hegde and DiAntonio, 2002; Schorova and Martin, 2016; Takahashi et al., 2003),
99 trafficking and biophysical properties of NT receptors (Diering and Haganir, 2018; Luscher et al., 2011;
100 Schorova and Martin, 2016), PSD organization (Coba, 2019; Zacchi et al., 2014) and synaptic adhesion (Jeong
101 et al., 2017). Beyond the essential roles of PTMs in brain physiology, their impairment is thought to critically
102 contribute to the etiology of several brain disorders including synaptopathies. Among PTMs, ubiquitination
103 and ubiquitin-like proteins (UBLs) such as sumoylation and neddylation share multiple features, tightly
104 interplay and are vital to synapse assembly, maturation and function. In this review, we focus on the role of
105 ubiquitination, sumoylation and neddylation in synapse physiology and their implication in the molecular
106 pathogenesis of intellectual disability (ID), a generalized neurodevelopmental disorder that manifests in a wide
107 range of brain pathologies (Picker and Walsh, 2013; Verpelli and Sala, 2012; Vissers et al., 2016).

108

109 **UBIQUITINATION AND UBL PATHWAYS IN SYNAPSE PHYSIOLOGY**

110 **Ubiquitination**

111 Ubiquitination occurs in all eukaryotic cells. It consists in the reversible conjugation of the 76 amino acid (aa)-
112 long ubiquitin protein to lysine (K) residues of target proteins. This process is catalyzed by a series of
113 enzymatic reactions. E1 ubiquitin enzymes bind to and activate free ubiquitin through adenylation at ubiquitin
114 C-terminal and thiol transfer. Activated ubiquitin is then transferred to E2 ubiquitin-conjugating enzymes and
115 finally transferred onto a K residue of target proteins by E3 ubiquitin ligases. Protein substrates can be either

116 mono- or poly-ubiquitinated and ubiquitin chains can vary depending on which of the seven K residues of
117 ubiquitin is used to covalently attach the subsequent ubiquitin (for a comprehensive review refer to (Komander
118 and Rape, 2012)). The human genome encodes two E1, ~50 E2 and ~600 E3 enzymes. Thus, substrate
119 specificity mainly relies on E3 ligases and different combinations of E2-E3 proteins. Ubiquitination is
120 counterbalanced by the action of deubiquitinating enzymes (DUBs) that remove ubiquitin from target proteins.
121 The coordinated activity of ubiquitinating enzymes and DUBs is essential to set and maintain ubiquitin
122 homeostasis (Kowalski and Juo, 2012).

123 Protein degradation through the ubiquitin proteasome system (UPS) is the best characterized function of
124 ubiquitination and K48 poly-ubiquitin chains are the most common signal to target proteins for degradation.
125 Conversely, mono-ubiquitination and K63 poly-ubiquitin chains mediate non-proteasomal functions and
126 typically modulate phosphorylation-dependent protein activation, protein-protein interactions and membrane
127 protein trafficking (Komander and Rape, 2012). Both proteasomal and non-proteasomal ubiquitin conjugations
128 occur at the synapse, where they regulate molecular processes important for synapse formation, maturation
129 and plasticity. As a consequence, ubiquitination is critical for long-term memory formation and stability as
130 observed with a variety of behavioral paradigms (reviewed in (Jarome and Helmstetter, 2013)).

131

132 Presynaptic ubiquitination

133 The importance of ubiquitination to the presynaptic function was first described in *Drosophila* neuromuscular
134 junctions (NMJs). Pharmacological and genetic perturbations of the UPS lead to the accumulation of Dunc-13,
135 a protein important for SV release, and significantly increase presynaptic efficacy (Speese et al., 2003). In line
136 with this, *Dunc-13* mouse ortholog, Munc-13 is also ubiquitinated by the E3 ligase Fbxo45 in the
137 hippocampus (Tada et al., 2010) (Fig. 1A). Syntaxin 1 (Stx1), a major component of the SNAP REceptor
138 (SNARE) complex and the binding partner of the presynaptic Ca²⁺ sensor synaptotagmin (Rizo and Xu, 2015)
139 is poly-ubiquitinated by the E3 enzyme Staring (Chin et al., 2002) (Fig. 1A). Ubiquitination further regulates
140 NT release by targeting the presynaptically expressed group III metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGlu) 7,
141 which inhibit glutamate or GABA release (Niswender and Conn, 2010). Upon stimulation with L-glutamate,
142 the E3 ligase Nedd4 induces rapid mGlu7 internalization and degradation via both proteasomal and lysosomal

143 pathways (Lee et al., 2019) (Fig. 1A). Protein degradation via the UPS is also a major regulator of SV
144 recycling (Willeumier et al., 2006). Interestingly, blocking action potentials with tetrodotoxin (TTX) prevents
145 the effect of proteasome inhibition on the recycling vesicle pool, suggesting that presynaptic UPS may be a
146 negative feedback-regulator of synaptic transmission.

147 Beside basal synaptic transmission, presynaptic ubiquitination is also a critical determinant of synaptic
148 plasticity and is required for cognition. Genetic deletion of the anaphase-promoting complex/cyclosome
149 (APC/C) in the forebrain of adult mice impairs hippocampal-dependent memories, such as spatial memory and
150 extinction of fear memory resulting in anxiety-related behaviors (Kuczera et al., 2010; Li et al., 2008). Whilst
151 at *Drosophila* and *C. elegans* NMJs it is known that APC/C targets the active zone protein Liprin- α (Kowalski
152 et al., 2014; van Roessel et al., 2004), the presynaptic targets in mammals remains elusive. Recently, the E3
153 ligase RNF8 was shown to be required to build up cerebellar circuits mediating procedural motor learning by
154 limiting the formation of parallel fiber presynaptic boutons onto Purkinje cells by targeting as yet unidentified
155 substrates (Valnegri et al., 2017). Another presynaptic E3 ligase fundamental to establish neuronal
156 connectivity is Scrapper. In mouse hippocampal neurons, Scrapper modulates multiple aspects of the
157 presynaptic function by directly ubiquitinating and regulating Rab3-interacting protein 1 (RIM1) (Fig. 1A).
158 Consistent with the role of RIM1 as major SV priming factor (Südhof, 2004), axonal boutons of Scrapper-
159 knock out (KO) neurons show enhanced synaptic transmission, owing a significant increase of NT release
160 probability (Takagi et al., 2012; Yao et al., 2007). Moreover, the absence of Scrapper expression interferes
161 with performances in contextual fear conditioning tests and hippocampi derived from these mice exhibit
162 bidirectional changes of synaptic plasticity regulation (also referred to as metaplasticity) (Takagi et al., 2012;
163 Yao et al., 2011). These cellular and behavioral features partially recapitulate defects observed in RIM1-KO
164 animals (Castillo et al., 2002; Powell et al., 2004), although there may be other Scrapper synaptic targets.
165 Finally, a spontaneous mutation in the *usp14* gene, encoding the proteasome-associated deubiquitinating
166 enzyme Usp14 (Fig. 1A), leads to progressive locomotor defects and ataxia (Wilson et al., 2002). Loss of
167 *usp14* results in impaired short-term facilitation and reduced SV number, indicating the importance of a
168 balanced ubiquitination to preserve presynaptic functions (Walters et al., 2014). However, which proteins are
169 targeted by Usp14 and whether Usp14 facilitates or inhibits presynaptic UPS are still unclear.

170 Intriguingly, two large scaffolding proteins of the active zone, Piccolo and Bassoon, were suggested to be
171 important regulators of presynaptic ubiquitination (Waites et al., 2013). Interference with the expression of
172 these genes leads to aberrant degradation of proteins operating in the active zone and degeneration of
173 presynaptic boutons. As this phenotype is partially rescued by either the inhibition of the proteasome or the
174 downregulation of the E3 ligase Siah1, it is likely that Piccolo and Bassoon limit presynaptic ubiquitination
175 via the suppression of Siah1 activity.

176 Altogether, the aforementioned studies clearly indicate that ubiquitination is critical to NT release, the primary
177 function of presynaptic terminals, and, at the circuit level participates to memory and learning processes.

178

179 Postsynaptic ubiquitination

180 At the postsynaptic site, ubiquitination is a key mechanism that shapes the functional organization of both
181 excitatory and inhibitory synapses by targeting multiple categories of postsynaptic proteins (Fig. 1A, C).
182 Consistent with this, the proteasome is rapidly recruited and trapped into dendritic spines, the major site for
183 excitatory synapses, after membrane depolarization (Bingol et al., 2010; Bingol and Schuman, 2006).

184 One of the most well-studied ubiquitinated NT receptors are the α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-
185 isoxazolepropionic acid receptors (AMPA receptors) (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2). They are glutamate-gated ion channels
186 (also referred to as ionotropic glutamate receptors, iGluRs) and mediate the fast excitatory transmission in the
187 brain (Greger et al., 2017). The regulation of their number at the synaptic surface is a major determinant of
188 synaptic strength and plasticity (Choquet and Triller, 2013; Huganir and Nicoll, 2013). The importance of
189 AMPAR ubiquitination was first demonstrated in *C. elegans*, where it controls synaptic abundance of these
190 receptors and locomotor behavior (Burbea et al., 2002; Dreier et al., 2005; Emtage et al., 2009; Juo and
191 Kaplan, 2004). In mammals, the selective ubiquitination of GluA1 and GluA2 subunits is required for the
192 activity-dependent endocytosis of surface AMPARs directing them towards degradative pathways.
193 Ubiquitination occurs at K residues of their intracellular C-terminal tail via the E3 ligase Nedd4-1 and
194 RNF167 (Lussier et al., 2012, 2011; Schwarz et al., 2010). Finally, a more recent study showed that activity-
195 dependent AMPAR ubiquitination involves all four GluA subunits (GluA1-4) and sorts AMPARs from early
196 to late endosomes and subsequent lysosome-dependent degradation (Widagdo et al., 2015). Considering that

197 the modulation of AMPAR number at synaptic sites tunes synaptic strength and plasticity, it is expected that
198 AMPAR ubiquitination has implication in learning and memory paradigms. Consistently, proteasome
199 inhibition increases synaptic surface GluA1-containing AMPARs and enhances fear-conditioned learning
200 (Yeh et al., 2006). UPS-dependent degradation of GluA1 also facilitates the extinction of fear memories,
201 which is mediated by NMDAR-dependent depression of synaptic activity (Mao et al., 2008). AMPAR
202 ubiquitination is finely counteracted by the opposite action of a few DUBs. Overexpression of Usp46 prolongs
203 GluA1 half-life, resulting in enhanced amplitude of excitatory postsynaptic currents (Huo et al., 2015). Usp8
204 antagonizes the E3 ligase Nedd4-1 and is involved in downscaling synaptic strength during homeostatic
205 plasticity, providing the first evidence for an opposed bidirectional control of synaptic strength by
206 ubiquitination (Scudder et al., 2014).

207 Among the iGluR family, *N*-methyl-D-aspartate receptors (NMDARs) play an essential role in synaptic
208 plasticity (Paoletti et al., 2013) and their function, similarly to other iGluR members, is modulated by
209 ubiquitination (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2). The GluN2B, GluN2D, GluN1 and GluN2A subunits are targeted by the
210 E3 ubiquitin ligases Mind bomb-2 (Mib2), Nedd4 and Fbxo2 (Atkin et al., 2015; Gautam et al., 2013; Jurd et
211 al., 2008; Kato et al., 2005). Upon phosphorylation-dependent ubiquitination of GluN2B by Mib2 in the PSD,
212 NMDAR-mediated currents are significantly reduced. This effect is prevented when cells are treated with the
213 proteasome inhibitor MG132, suggesting that ubiquitinated GluN2B undergoes UPS-dependent degradation
214 (Jurd et al., 2008). Similarly, Nedd4 selectively conjugates poly-ubiquitin chains to GluN2D and reduces
215 NMDAR currents in heterologous cells (Gautam et al., 2013). Whether ubiquitination directly mediates
216 GluN2D proteasome-dependent degradation or modulates receptor endocytosis and sorting to late endosomes
217 and lysosomes is not known. Conversely, Fbxo2 ubiquitinates newly synthesized GluN1 and GluN2A subunits
218 in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and mediates its degradation via the ER-associated degradation (ERAD)
219 machinery, a mechanism that avoids the formation of supra-numerary synapses in the dendritic shaft and
220 aberrant NMDAR-mediated currents (Atkin et al., 2015; Gascón et al., 2007; Kato et al., 2005; Nelson et al.,
221 2006). Synaptic abundance and clustering of GluN1-containing NMDARs are also modulated by the
222 hominoid-specific DUB USP6 (Zeng et al., 2019). By generating a humanized knock-in (KI) mouse
223 expressing USP6 under the control of CaMKII promoter, the authors found that USP6 stabilizes NMDARs at

224 synapses and enhances synaptic function resulting in improved mouse cognitive abilities. Beside the novel
225 synaptic mechanism uncovered here, this study suggests for the first time that ubiquitination may have
226 contributed to the evolution of human-specific synaptic features, which are thought to form, together with
227 other processes the cellular basis of human intelligence (DeFelipe, 2011; Geschwind and Rakic, 2013). In line
228 with this, perturbation of USP6 is associated with human-specific neuropsychiatric disorders, such as ID (Ou
229 et al., 2006) and ASD (Tentler et al., 2003).

230 Kainate receptors (KARs) are the third receptor subtypes of iGluRs whose activity and trafficking are
231 modulated by ubiquitination (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2). The E3 ligases Cullin 3 (Cul3) and Parkin 2 (PARK2) target
232 the GluK2 subunit of KARs and regulate its surface expression (Maraschi et al., 2014; Salinas et al., 2006).
233 Strikingly, loss-of function of PARK2, which is causative of the most common form of familial juvenile
234 parkinsonism, leads to abnormal levels of synaptic GluK2, a mechanism that could underlie glutamate
235 excitotoxicity and neurodegeneration in Parkinson's disease. Yet, it is unclear whether KAR ubiquitination
236 occurs on surface receptors and whether it is degraded through UPS or lysosomal pathway.

237 Metabotropic glutamate receptors (mGluRs) are also targeted by ubiquitination at the postsynaptic
238 compartment (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2). Upon dihydroxyphenylglycine (DHPG)-induced activation of group I
239 mGlu1 and 5 receptors, the E3 ligase Siah-1A attaches K63-linked poly-ubiquitin chains to intracellular K
240 residues of these receptors and induces their internalization (Gulia et al., 2017; Ko et al., 2012; Moriyoshi et
241 al., 2004). Since their activation is critical for the expression of long-term depression (LTD) (Niswender and
242 Conn, 2010), mGluR ubiquitination emerged as an essential regulatory mechanism limiting excessive synaptic
243 depression (Gulia et al., 2017).

244 As aforementioned, postsynaptic scaffolding proteins are the structural core of the PSD. Here, complex
245 protein-protein interactions are tightly regulated by PTMs to control the functional organization of synapses
246 (Sheng and Hoogenraad, 2007). Given the multiple protein-protein interactions that each scaffolding protein
247 engages, the ubiquitination of a few scaffolding proteins allows the precise regulation of a large set of
248 postsynaptic molecules (Fig. 1A). PSD-95, GKAP, AKAP79/150, Shank and Homer1A are abundant
249 scaffolding proteins of excitatory synapses and their levels are bidirectionally modulated by ubiquitination in
250 an activity-dependent manner (Ageta et al., 2001; Colledge et al., 2003; Ehlers, 2003; Na et al., 2012; Rezvani

251 et al., 2007). Importantly, the targeted degradation of scaffolding molecules critically contributes to learning
252 and behavior. Retrieval of fear memory up-regulates polyubiquitinated Shank and GKAP, but not PSD95.
253 Consistent with this, infusion of the proteasome inhibitor clasto-lactacystin- β -lactone in the CA1 region of the
254 hippocampus immediately after retrieval prevents extinction of fear memory (Lee et al., 2008). To date, only
255 few of the E3 ligases targeting scaffolding proteins were identified. The E3 ligase Mdm2 ubiquitinates PSD-95
256 at multiple residues and induces distinct pathways. The mono-ubiquitination of PSD-95 within the PEST
257 (peptides rich in Proline, Glutamate, Serine, and Threonine) motif, a short sequence serving as proteolytic
258 signal, triggers PSD-95 degradation. As a consequence, the number of PSD-95 molecules available to anchor
259 AMPARs is reduced, resulting in less stable surface AMPARs and enhanced endocytosis (Fig. 2), a
260 mechanism that critically contributes to hippocampal LTD (Colledge et al., 2003). Conversely, the Cdk5-
261 dependent ubiquitination of PSD-95 at K10 promotes its interaction with and the recruitment of the clathrin
262 adaptor protein complex (AP)2 at the synapse, triggering clathrin-dependent AMPAR endocytosis (Bianchetta
263 et al., 2011). The ubiquitination of GKAP, mediated by the E3 ubiquitin ligase TRIM3, induces structural
264 changes of dendritic spines (Hung et al., 2010). Whilst the enzymes mediating Shank ubiquitination are not
265 known, it has been recently identified that Usp8 selectively deubiquitinates Shank1 and 3 and modulates
266 dendritic spine density and morphology (Campbell and Sheng, 2018).

267 Among postsynaptic signaling proteins, the ubiquitination of the immediate early gene activity-regulated
268 cytoskeleton-associated protein Arc is best characterized (Fig. 1A and Fig 2). Arc responds to various forms of
269 synaptic plasticity and promotes the endocytosis of AMPARs (Shepherd et al., 2006; Waung et al., 2008).
270 *UBE3A* is the main causal gene of a severe neurodevelopmental disorder, the Angelman syndrome (AS), and
271 encodes the first E3 ligase proposed to target Arc (Greer et al., 2010). Since *UBE3A* is also a transcriptional
272 co-regulator (Nawaz et al., 1999), it is unclear whether *UBE3A*-dependent regulation of Arc operates at the
273 protein level through ubiquitination or at the transcriptional level (Kuhnle et al., 2013). Other studies indicated
274 that Arc is ubiquitinated by the E3 ligase Triad3 (Mabb et al., 2014; Na et al., 2012). Another signaling protein
275 targeted by ubiquitination is the spine-associated Rap GTPase activating protein (SPAR) (Fig. 1A). SPAR
276 forms a complex with PSD-95 and NMDARs and is critical for spine structural plasticity (Pak et al., 2001).
277 Upon induction of synaptic down-scaling, phosphorylated SPAR is ubiquitinated by the E3 ligase complex

278 SCF^{βTRPC} resulting in its degradation and spine morphology changes (Ang et al., 2008; Pak and Sheng, 2003).
279 Eventually, proteomic approaches aimed at identifying synaptic ubiquitome in rat brains revealed that the
280 Ca²⁺/Calmodulin-dependent kinase II (CaMKII), which is crucial for the expression of synaptic plasticity
281 (Coultrap and Bayer, 2012), is ubiquitinated (Na et al., 2012) (Fig. 1A). Yet, the identity of the E3 ligase that
282 targets CaMKII, the consequences on CaMKII stability and the functional relevance for plasticity remain to be
283 assessed.

284 Ubiquitination was also studied at inhibitory synapses (Fig. 1C). The number of surface GABA_ARs is critically
285 modulated by the ubiquitin-associated chaperon Plic-1 (also named ubiquilin) (Bedford et al., 2001; Zhang et
286 al., 2015). Given the association of Plic proteins with the proteasome in the ER (Kleijnen et al., 2000), it was
287 proposed that Plic-1 inhibits GABA_AR degradation via ERAD (Bedford et al., 2001; Saliba et al., 2008).
288 Accordingly, synaptic up- and down-regulation of surface GABA_ARs are governed by changes in poly-
289 ubiquitination dynamics of newly synthesized β3 subunits in the ER (Saliba et al., 2007) (Fig. 2). In contrast,
290 the ubiquitination of the γ2 subunit does not alter the forward-directed biosynthetic route, but instead triggers
291 GABA_AR endocytosis and subsequent lysosome-dependent degradation (Arancibia-Carcamo et al., 2009; Jin
292 et al., 2014) (Fig. 2). In the cerebellum, the Usp14-dependent deubiquitination of the α1 subunit, which is
293 contained in the majority of cerebellar GABA_ARs, reduces surface GABA_ARs and favors receptor sorting
294 towards lysosomal compartments (Lappe-Siefke et al., 2009) (Fig. 1C). At inhibitory synapses, unlike their
295 glutamatergic counterparts, no scaffolding proteins were found ubiquitinated, so far. Notwithstanding,
296 gephyrin, the major scaffolding protein of inhibitory synapses (Tyagarajan and Fritschy, 2014), contains two
297 PEST sequences (Tyagarajan et al., 2011). Whether these PEST motifs, as that of PSD-95, are targeted by
298 ubiquitination is unclear.

299 Collectively, there is strong evidence that ubiquitination targets multiple synaptic components and represents a
300 complex regulatory system controlling synapse formation, maintenance and plasticity. In line with this,
301 ubiquitination is also required for learning and memory. However, the molecular logic of how the ubiquitin
302 system controls cognition and how targeted ubiquitination determines specific behavioral outputs remain
303 enigmatic.

304

305 **Sumoylation**

306 Sumoylation consists in the covalent but reversible conjugation of the 100 aa-long Small Ubiquitin-like
307 Modifier (SUMO) protein to specific K residues of substrates (refer to (Flotho and Melchior, 2013) for a more
308 comprehensive review). Like ubiquitination, sumoylation requires a dedicated enzymatic pathway and its
309 homeostasis is finely regulated by conjugating and deconjugating enzymes. SUMO is first synthesized as a
310 non-conjugatable precursor that is cleaved by Sentrin-proteases (SENPs) to generate a mature SUMO
311 molecule. Mature SUMO is subsequently activated by heterodimers of SUMO-activating enzymes (SAE) 1
312 and 2 in an ATP-dependent manner and transferred to the catalytic cysteine of the sole SUMO-specific
313 conjugating enzyme Ubc9. Ubc9 finally catalyzes SUMO conjugation to designated substrates. Targeted K
314 residues typically localize within the consensus motif Ψ -K-x-E, where Ψ is a hydrophobic residue and x is any
315 amino acid. SUMO deconjugation occurs through the activity of SENPs. Mammalian cells express three
316 different SUMO paralogues (SUMO1-3) and six SENPs (SEN1-3, 5-7). As all PTMs, sumoylation modulates
317 the function of target proteins by distinct mechanisms. It can (i) trigger conformational changes that affect
318 protein activity; (ii) inhibit or favor protein-protein interactions by either generating or masking a binding site;
319 (iii) control substrate stability and turnover through a SUMO-mediated recruitment of members of the SUMO-
320 targeted ubiquitin ligase family (Flotho and Melchior, 2013).

321 Originally, sumoylation was described as nuclear modification regulating protein translocation across the
322 nuclear membrane and transcription (Mahajan et al., 1997; Matunis et al., 1996). Since then, many other
323 SUMO substrates were identified inside and outside the nuclear compartment, including synapses. It is now
324 well-accepted that sumoylation controls several processes critical for neuronal function such as neuronal
325 excitability and synapse development and plasticity (Henley et al., 2018; Schorova and Martin, 2016). During
326 brain development, the SUMO machinery and neuronal sumoylome dynamics are tightly regulated in a
327 spatiotemporal manner. In the brain, the overall expression of SUMO components and SUMO-conjugated
328 proteins peaks during late stages of embryonic development (embryonic days, (E)13-18) and rapidly decreases
329 postnatally (Hasegawa et al., 2014; Josa-Prado et al., 2019; Loriol et al., 2012; Watanabe et al., 2008). In
330 addition, these proteins are redistributed from the nucleus to the synapse after birth (Loriol et al., 2012), where
331 sumoylation still occurs in mature cortical/hippocampal neurons and is rapidly enhanced by neuronal activity

332 (Colnaghi et al., 2019; Loriol et al., 2013). According to the critical role of sumoylation in controlling synaptic
333 function, Ubc9 and SENP1 enzymes dynamically diffuse inside and outside dendritic spines in an activity-
334 dependent manner (Loriol et al., 2014; Schorova et al., 2019). The activation of mGlu5R triggers the transient
335 trapping of Ubc9 in the head of dendritic spines, leading to a rapid increase in synaptic sumoylation (Loriol et
336 al., 2014). Ubc9 recruitment is followed by time-dependent decrease in the exit rate of SENP1 from dendritic
337 spines, resulting in the post-synaptic accumulation of SENP1, which restores synaptic sumoylation to initial
338 levels (Schorova et al., 2019). Moreover, perturbation of SUMO homeostasis affects synapse physiology and
339 consequently impacts cognitive functions. Decreasing sumoylation levels by overexpressing either a dominant
340 negative form of Ubc9 or the catalytic domain of SENP1 prevents the increase of surface AMPARs upon LTP
341 induction, indicating that sumoylation is essential for the expression of synaptic plasticity (Jaafari et al., 2013).
342 Accordingly, acute inhibition of sumoylation impairs hippocampal-dependent learning and memory in mice
343 (Lee et al., 2015). Neuron-specific silencing of *SUMO1-3* induces anxiety-like responses and impaired
344 episodic memory providing the first evidence that SUMO conjugation is essential for emotionality and
345 cognition (Wang et al., 2014). Conversely, increase of global SUMO1-ylation in SUMO1 transgenic mice or
346 by chronic infusion of exogenous SUMO1 impairs learning and memory performances (Matsuzaki et al.,
347 2015; Yoo et al., 2017). Furthermore, the loss of SENP2 in conditional KO mice results in several behavioral
348 defects including spatial working memory impairment (Huang et al., 2020). RNA sequencing also revealed
349 that the expression of genes critical for learning and memory is finely regulated by SENP2.
350 Together, these findings pointed out that sumoylation is essential to synapse development and function and a
351 balanced sumoylation/desumoylation is crucial for learning and memory processes. In line with this, over the
352 last decade, several groups identified novel SUMO targets critical to synaptic function (Henley et al., 2018;
353 Schorova and Martin, 2016).

354

355 *Extrasynaptic sumoylation critical to the synaptic function*

356 The first identified SUMO substrates bearing synaptic functions were components of the myocyte enhancer
357 factor 2 (MEF2) family of transcription factors (Fig. 1B). *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies showed that sumoylation
358 represses the transcriptional activity of MEF2A, MEF2C and MEF2D (Grégoire et al., 2006; Kang et al.,

359 2006; Shalizi et al., 2006). In particular, MEF2A sumoylation at K403 is critical for dendritic claw
360 differentiation in the cerebellum via transcriptional inhibition of the transcription factor Nur77 (Shalizi et al.,
361 2006). Interestingly, MEF2A sumoylation is tightly modulated by neuronal activity and requires a complex
362 crosstalk with other PTMs. The Ca²⁺-dependent phosphatase calcineurin dephosphorylates MEF2A at Serine
363 (S)408 and triggers the switch of K403 from being sumoylated to acetylated, resulting in the activation of
364 MEF2A. Acetylated MEF2A thus enhances Nur77 transcription and leads to the inhibition of dendritic claw
365 formation. Subsequently, it was also demonstrated that MEF2A sumoylation is critical for presynaptic
366 differentiation by regulating the transcription of synaptotagmin 1, thus indicating that MEF2A sumoylation
367 has a broader role in synaptic development (Shalizi et al., 2007).

368 A second extrasynaptic target of the SUMO machinery is the DNA binding protein and transcriptional
369 repressor Methyl-CpG binding Protein 2 (MeCP2) (Fig. 1B). Sumoylation at K223 of MeCP2 is required for
370 the recruitment of histone deacetylase complexes 1/2 (HDAC 1/2) and the consequent repression of gene
371 expression, an essential event for the correct development of hippocampal excitatory synapses *in vitro* and *in*
372 *vivo* (Cheng et al., 2014). Conversely, sumoylation at K412 decreases the physical interaction between MeCP2
373 and the cAMP response element binding protein (CREB), which ultimately enhances the transcription of the
374 brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) transcription (Tai et al., 2016). Similar to MEF2A, MeCP2
375 phosphorylation in nearby residues (S421 and threonine, T, 308) facilitates MeCP2 sumoylation, further
376 highlighting the functional interplay between distinct PTMs. As described below, mutations in *MECP2* gene
377 are associated with neurodevelopmental disorders, among which the Rett syndrome (RTT) is the most
378 prevalent (Guy et al., 2011).

379 Recently, two other transcription factors, FOXP1 and FOXP2, were found sumoylated (Fig. 1B). These factors
380 are required for the assembly of cerebellar circuits underlying vocalization and motor skills (Bacon and
381 Rappold, 2012). FOXP2 sumoylation at K674 regulates its transcriptional activity (Estruch et al., 2016;
382 Meredith et al., 2016) and mediates dendritic outgrowth and arborization of Purkinje cells (Usui et al., 2017).
383 In line with this, individuals from a family affected by speech and language disorders display a significant
384 reduction of sumoylated FOXP2, supporting the pivotal role of FOXP2 sumoylation for the acquisition of
385 these communication skills (Meredith et al., 2016). Similarly to FOXP2, FOXP1 sumoylation at K670 is

386 indispensable for dendritic outgrowth and complexity in cortical neurons via inhibition of FOXP1
387 transcriptional activity (Rocca et al., 2017). Remarkably, the autism-linked *CNTNAP2* gene, which promotes
388 the development of dendritic arbors, is transcriptionally repressed by sumoylated FOXP1, suggesting a
389 potential molecular mechanism underlying FOXP1 function during neuronal development (Rocca et al., 2017).
390 Fragile X Mental Retardation Protein (FMRP) is the most recently identified extrasynaptic SUMO target with
391 synaptic roles (Khayachi et al., 2018) (Fig. 1B). FMRP is an RNA-binding protein and a key component of
392 neuronal mRNA granules. In these granules, FMRP transports translationally-repressed mRNAs along axons
393 and dendrites to the base of active synapses, where their local translation is a key process for synapse
394 maturation and plasticity (Prieto et al., 2019). The rapid activation of mGlu5R results in FMRP sumoylation at
395 K88 and K130, which triggers the dissociation of FMRP from mRNA granules and enables the local
396 translation of mRNAs that control dendritic spine elimination and maturation (Khayachi et al., 2018). It
397 remains to be elucidated whether FMRP sumoylation discharges the whole set of mRNA molecules associated
398 with FRMP or promotes the release of a specific subset of these mRNAs.

399

400 Presynaptic sumoylation

401 At the presynaptic compartment, sumoylation regulates diverse functions. Synaptosomal fractions loaded with
402 purified SUMO1 display a significant reduction of Ca^{2+} influx and KCl-evoked glutamate release.
403 Accordingly, Ca^{2+} influx and KCl-evoked glutamate release are enhanced in synapses supplemented with
404 SENP1 (Feligioni et al., 2009). Intriguingly, modulation of synaptic sumoylation produces the reverse effect
405 on glutamate release evoked by kainate stimulation. These results suggest that different stimuli triggers
406 sumoylation of distinct presynaptic proteins to either inhibit or promote NT release (Feligioni et al., 2009). A
407 primary presynaptic function controlled by the SUMO pathway is SV docking/priming through sumoylation of
408 RIM1 α and synapsin Ia (SynIa) (Fig. 1A). Sumoylation of SynIa triggers its association with SVs and
409 facilitates SV anchoring at the presynaptic membrane (Tang et al., 2015). Similarly, RIM1 α sumoylation at
410 K502 promotes its interaction with the voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels (Ca_v) 2.1, favoring their clustering at the
411 presynaptic membrane and enhancing the Ca^{2+} influx required for NT release (Girach et al., 2013).
412 Conversely, non-sumoylated RIM1 α prevents Ca_v 2.1 clustering and increases SV docking in the active zone.

413 Thus, the switch between the sumoylated and non-sumoylated state of RIM1 α is a key determinant for the fast
414 and synchronous NT release.

415 Sumoylation also directly controls SV exocytosis by targeting Stx1A (Craig et al., 2016) (Fig. 1A). Indeed,
416 sumoylated Stx1A is more associated with two other components of the SNARE complex, SNAP-25 and
417 VAMP-2, providing the mechanical forces required for SV exocytosis. Indeed, preventing Stx1A sumoylation
418 reduces its interaction with SNARE proteins and disrupts the balance of SV endo/exocytosis, skewing towards
419 endocytosis.

420 In 2015, Matsuzaki and colleagues generated a transgenic mouse line overexpressing *SUMO1* in neurons
421 aiming to identify the neuronal sumoylome (Matsuzaki et al., 2015). Among the 95 SUMO1 substrates
422 identified by mass spectrometry (MS), only synaptotagmin-1 was further validated biochemically (Fig. 1A).
423 Nevertheless, further investigations are required to exclude possible off-target sumoylation owing to SUMO1
424 overexpression.

425 Regarding mGluRs, the majority of group III mGluRs were identified as SUMO substrates in primary cultured
426 neurons and heterologous cells (Dütting et al., 2011; Seebahn et al., 2008; Tang et al., 2005; Wilkinson and
427 Henley, 2011) (Fig. 1A). However, mGlu7R is the sole member shown to be sumoylated in brain tissues. Like
428 other SUMO targets, its sumoylation has to be preceded by PKC-dependent phosphorylation at S862 (Choi et
429 al., 2016). Opposed to its ubiquitination, mGlu7R sumoylation stabilizes its expression at the cell surface.
430 Therefore, ubiquitination and sumoylation of mGlu7R bidirectionally modulate its surface expression at the
431 presynaptic membrane and ultimately, regulate NT release. The type-1 endocannabinoid (CB1) receptors are
432 another class of metabotropic receptors that regulates presynaptic functions (Castillo et al., 2012).
433 Interestingly, it was shown that conjugated and unconjugated SUMO1 levels transiently increase upon CB1
434 activation as well as CB1 itself might be targeted by SUMO (Gowran et al., 2009). However, further
435 experiments are needed to confirm this hypothesis.

436 Among the voltage-gated ion channels targeted by sumoylation, potassium channels are the most represented
437 (Fig. 1A). SENP2-deficient mice display hypersumoylation of voltage-gated potassium (K_v) 1.1 and 7.2/7.3
438 channels. While sumoylation of K_v1.1 does not alter channel activity, enhanced sumoylation of K_v7.2 reduces
439 depolarizing M-currents, resulting in neuronal hyperexcitability and epileptic seizures (Qi et al., 2014).

440 Similarly, sumoylation of surface $K_v2.1$ reduces channel activity and as a consequence, enhances neuronal
441 excitability (Plant et al., 2011). Interestingly, $K_v4.2$ was recently found sumoylated in two distinct sites,
442 producing different effects (Welch et al., 2019). While sumoylation at K437 triggers $K_v4.2$ surface expression,
443 sumoylation at K579 decreases the amplitude of K currents, without any change in $K_v4.2$ trafficking.
444 Differently, the sumoylation of voltage-gated sodium (Na_v) 1.2 channels enhances the amplitude of Na^+
445 currents (Plant et al., 2016) (Fig. 1A).

446 Moreover, sumoylation is also essential to control the axonal trafficking and function of $Na_v1.7$ by targeting
447 the collapsin response mediator protein 2 (CRMP2) (Fig. 1A). CRMP2 is highly expressed in the brain and is
448 critical for microtubule remodeling, neuronal polarity, axon outgrowth and synapse dynamics (Arimura et al.,
449 2004; Zhang et al., 2016). Expression of a CRMP2 SUMO-deficient mutant prevents its physical interaction
450 with $Na_v1.7$ and decreases $Na_v1.7$ surface expression, resulting in reduced amplification of membrane
451 depolarization in presynaptic boutons (Dustrude et al., 2017, 2013; Ju et al., 2013). CRMP2 sumoylation is
452 also phosphorylation-dependent (Dustrude et al., 2016). Indeed, interfering with either CRMP2 sumoylation or
453 phosphorylation reduces surface $Na_v1.7$. Beside its presynaptic role, CRMP2 also interacts with the actin
454 cytoskeleton in dendrites and dendritic spines. It was recently found that desumoylation and
455 dephosphorylation of CRMP2 independently promote the formation and maturation of dendritic spines,
456 broadening the importance of PTMs in regulating the multiple functions of CRMP2 (Zhang et al., 2018).

457 Beside targeted sumoylation, an intriguing concept that might also apply to synapses (Henley et al., 2018) is
458 that sumoylation may occur simultaneously to components of protein assemblies. This idea of a synchronous
459 “SUMO spray” on multiple targets (named “SUMO velcro”) was first shown to occur in the nucleus, where
460 DNA damage triggers a SUMO wave that activates multiple components of the enzymatic pathway required to
461 repair the DNA (Psakhye and Jentsch, 2012). In particular, though not yet experimentally validated, the model
462 of SUMO spray might properly suit to presynaptic NT release, which requires a coordinated series of protein-
463 protein interactions that are tightly regulated by sumoylation (Henley et al., 2018).

464

465 Postsynaptic sumoylation

466 To date, postsynaptic sumoylation has been less characterized than extrasynaptic and presynaptic sumoylation.
467 Nevertheless, the first identified synaptic target of the SUMO pathway was GluK2 (Martin et al., 2007) (Fig.
468 1A and Fig. 2). Kainate stimulation promotes GluK2 sumoylation at K886, triggering receptor endocytosis
469 during LTD expression at mossy fiber–CA3 synapses in the hippocampus (Chamberlain et al., 2012;
470 Konopacki et al., 2011; Martin et al., 2007). As for other SUMO targets, the PKC-dependent phosphorylation
471 of S868-GluK2 is required for its subsequent sumoylation (Chamberlain et al., 2012; Konopacki et al., 2011).
472 As aforementioned, GluK2 is also ubiquitinated. However, whether these two PTMs operate in synergy,
473 reciprocally compete or are independent remains to be investigated.

474 A second postsynaptic SUMO target is the calcium/calmodulin-dependent serine protein kinase (CASK) (Fig.
475 1A). CASK belongs to the membrane-associated guanylate kinase (MAGUK) family of scaffolding proteins
476 and is involved in dendritic spine formation and maturation through the modulation of the actin cytoskeleton
477 via the interaction with the protein 4.1 (Biederer and Südhof, 2001). The protein 4.1 binds spectrin and bridges
478 the association between F-actin and spectrin, stabilizing actin in dendritic spines. Conjugation of SUMO1 to
479 K679 of CASK interferes with the interaction between CASK and protein 4.1 and consequently, regulates
480 spine density and morphology in developing neurons (Chao et al., 2008).

481 Among postsynaptic signaling proteins, Arc, which is also ubiquitinated, is the sole SUMO target identified so
482 far (Craig et al., 2012; Craig and Henley, 2012) (Fig. 1A and Fig. 2). The expression of a constitutively
483 desumoylated Arc selectively prevents the increase of surface AMPARs during TTX-induced synaptic up-
484 scaling, indicating that sumoylation inhibits Arc function. Interestingly, the same treatment also augments the
485 amount of SUMO1-conjugated proteins and decreases SENP1 levels (Craig et al., 2012). Recently, it was
486 demonstrated that sumoylated Arc is more broadly implicated in synaptic plasticity. During LTP
487 consolidation, sumoylated Arc selectively accumulates in synaptosomal and cytoskeletal fractions, where it
488 forms a complex with the F-actin binding protein drebrin A, stabilizing nascent actin filaments in dendritic
489 spines (Nair et al., 2017). These results further support the role of sumoylation as master regulator of different
490 forms of synaptic plasticity.

491 At inhibitory synapses, gephyrin is extensively subjected to PTMs (Tyagarajan and Fritschy, 2014). In 2016, it
492 was shown that gephyrin sumoylation at K148 and K724 negatively regulates its postsynaptic clustering and,
493 ultimately, reduces synapse formation and inhibitory transmission (Fig. 1C). Gephyrin sumoylation is
494 intimately linked to other PTMs, which synergistically operate to orchestrate its clustering dynamics (Ghosh et
495 al., 2016). Desumoylation of gephyrin at K148 leads to deacetylation at K666 and dephosphorylation at S268
496 residues, enhancing its postsynaptic clustering and the assembly of inhibitory synapses.

497 Recently, the presence of SUMO1-conjugated proteins at synapses was questioned, bringing out an intense
498 scientific debate on this topic (Daniel et al., 2018, 2017; Tirard et al., 2012; Wilkinson et al., 2017). By using
499 KI mice expressing His₆-HA-SUMO1, Dr Brose and Dr Tirard teams were not able to validate sumoylation of
500 seven previously characterized pre- and postsynaptic SUMO targets nor to observe SUMO1 conjugation at
501 synapses (Daniel et al., 2017). On the contrary, they could confirm that extra-synaptic/nuclear sumoylation is
502 present (Tirard et al., 2012), concluding that there is no evidence of synaptic SUMO1-ylation.

503 Notwithstanding, several arguments support the presence of SUMO1-ylation at the synapse questioning if this
504 animal model is suitable to study sumoylation. *(i)* in His₆-HA-SUMO1 KI mice there is 20-30% less SUMO1
505 conjugation than WT mice, and this impairment is associated to a significant increase of SUMO2/3-conjugated
506 proteins (Daniel et al., 2017; Tirard et al., 2012). This reduction in the efficiency of SUMO1 conjugation could
507 make particularly challenging the detection of SUMO targets in the synaptic compartment where sumoylation
508 is already low and extremely transient; *(ii)* a wealth of studies confirmed the functional relevance of synaptic
509 sumoylation (e.g. use of non-sumoylatable mutants), while Daniel and colleagues did not carry out this
510 analysis (reviewed in (Henley et al., 2018; Schorova and Martin, 2016)); *(iii)* consistent data clearly indicate
511 the presence of components of the SUMO machinery at synaptic sites (Hasegawa et al., 2014; Josa-Prado et
512 al., 2019; Loriol et al., 2014, 2012; Schorova et al., 2019; Watanabe et al., 2008); *(iv)* some key technical
513 differences may explain the failure to detect synaptic sumoylation (e.g. weak SUMO1 immunostaining and the
514 use of antibodies that do not recognize sumoylated proteins). Altogether, though in our opinion substantial
515 data indicate the presence and the functional relevance of synaptic SUMO1-ylation, the aforementioned
516 studies pointed out the need of defining strict consensus criteria to investigate sumoylation in the brain.

517

518 **Neddylation**

519 Neddylation consists in the covalent and reversible attachment of a Nedd8 (for neural precursor cell expressed,
520 developmentally down-regulated 8) moiety to a K residue of target proteins. Of the UBLs, Nedd8 shows the
521 greatest degree of similarity with ubiquitin (~80%). Like ubiquitination and other UBLs, neddylation requires
522 a 3-step enzymatic cascade to activate and covalently attach Nedd8 to K residues of target proteins (Enchev et
523 al., 2015). Whilst E1 activating and E2 conjugating enzymes have been identified (Nedd8 activating enzyme,
524 NAE as E1, and UBC12 and UBE2F as E2 enzymes), the E3 ligases are as yet ill-defined. Deconjugation of
525 Nedd8 from targets is achieved by Nedd8-specific proteases, namely the metalloprotease Csn5, the cysteine
526 protease Nedp1 and Usp21 (Enchev et al., 2015).

527 Though Nedd8 function and regulation remain largely unexplored, recent papers shed light on the importance
528 of neddylation in synaptic maturation, function and plasticity. Neddylation is observed during embryonic brain
529 development, its expression increases during the first two postnatal weeks and is then maintained throughout
530 adulthood (Kumar et al., 1992; Vogl et al., 2015). As the best characterized function of Nedd8 involves the
531 activation of ubiquitin E3 ligases of the Cullin-RING family (Fig. 1A), neddylation is thought a major
532 regulator of ubiquitination (Enchev et al., 2015). In the hippocampus, NMDAR-dependent neddylation
533 promotes the UPS-dependent degradation of the DNA methyltransferase DNMT3a1 leading to demethylation
534 of the BDNF promoter and enabling BDNF expression during memory consolidation (Fig. 1A) (Bayraktar et
535 al., 2019). Among the members of the cullin-RING family, several ligases mediate the targeted degradation of
536 synaptic elements and negatively regulate synapses (e.g. cullin3 and parkin). However, inhibition of the
537 neddylation pathway does not enhance synaptic activity and strength as it would have been expected as a
538 consequence of reduced synaptic ubiquitination. Instead, it destabilizes dendritic spines, affects synaptic
539 transmission and plasticity, and impairs cognitive functions (Brockmann et al., 2019; Scudder and Patrick,
540 2015; Vogl et al., 2015), thus suggesting that neuronal neddylation targets other substrates relevant to synaptic
541 function. In line with this, Vogl and colleagues elegantly demonstrated that PSD95 is neddylated at K202 by
542 Mdm2 (Vogl et al., 2015), which also mediates PSD95 ubiquitination (Fig. 1A) (Bianchetta et al., 2011;
543 Colledge et al., 2003). Though PSD95 neddylation does not modify its ubiquitination and degradation rate,
544 neddylation reduces synaptic clustering of PSD95. Furthermore, the expression of a non-neddylatable mutant

545 recapitulates at least some of the molecular and cellular phenotypes observed with PSD95 knockdown (Ehrlich
546 et al., 2007) indicating that Nedd8-conjugation is required for PSD95 proactive functions. PSD95 is a major
547 molecular hub of excitatory synapses and mediates multiple interactions with several proteins (Sheng and
548 Kim, 2011). How neddylation changes PSD95 conformation and/or affinities with its partners remains to be
549 uncovered. Very recently, a Nedd8-ubiquitin substrate profiling detected 341 neddylated proteins in HEK293
550 cells expanding the repertoire of neddylated targets and indicating broader roles of neddylation than the sole
551 activation of cullin-RING E3 ligases (Vogl et al., 2020). Among the identified targets, the authors
552 biochemically and functionally characterized cofilin neddylation in the brain and found that it is required to
553 ensure proper dendrite development in mouse cortical neurons (Fig.1 A) (Vogl et al., 2020).

554

555 **ID AND IMPAIRMENT OF UBIQUITINATION AND SUMOYLATION PATHWAYS**

556 ID is a neurodevelopmental disorder with an estimated prevalence of 1-3%. The formal diagnosis of ID is
557 based on the intelligence quotient (IQ) test, which should be scored less than 70, and the presence of deficits in
558 at least two adaptive behaviors that affect every-day activities. It is classified as mild, moderate, severe or
559 profound based on IQ score. ID is defined as non-syndromic if the intellectual deficit is the sole clinical
560 feature, or as syndromic if the mental impairment is co-morbid with other neurological pathologies such as
561 epilepsy, sensory alterations and autism spectrum disorders (ASD) (Ilyas et al., 2020). ID is a complex
562 multifactorial disease, in which environmental and genetic factors and their reciprocal interaction critically
563 contribute to its etiology. Yet, 25% of ID cases have clear genetic origins and some of these forms are
564 monogenic. The environmental factors that underlie ID comprise stressful events occurring at early stages of
565 neurodevelopment, including drug and alcohol abuse and infections during pregnancy, birth complication and
566 severe malnutrition. Thanks to recent advances in whole-genome sequencing, the identification of genetic
567 defects is becoming increasingly efficient. To date, ~700 genes were associated to either syndromic or non-
568 syndromic ID. Notably, more than 50% of these genes encode pre- or postsynaptic proteins or proteins directly
569 or indirectly implicated in synapse development, function and plasticity (Ilyas et al., 2020). Among the several
570 genes associated with ID, ~100 genes are located on chromosome (chr.) X and are responsible for X-linked
571 intellectual disability (XLID) (Ropers and Hamel, 2005).

572 Numerous ID-associated genes code for proteins targeted by ubiquitination and sumoylation or components of
573 ubiquitin and SUMO machineries. Furthermore, some extrinsic risk factors of ID seem to be associated with
574 alterations of brain ubiquitome and/or sumoylome. In addition, as described above, several studies indicate
575 that ubiquitination and sumoylation are critical to the expression of synaptic plasticity, the cellular correlate of
576 learning and memory processes and whose impairment is a major hallmark of ID (Aicardi, 1998). Collectively,
577 this evidence suggests that ubiquitination and sumoylation failure may be implicated in ID pathogenesis.
578 Despite pharmacological or genetic blockade of neddylation results in cognitive dysfunctions that may
579 manifest in ID patients (e.g. impaired memory and sociability) (Vogl et al., 2015), current evidence does not
580 indicate a direct involvement of neddylation in the development of ID. Below we provide an overview of the
581 ID forms that are linked to defective ubiquitin and SUMO pathways.

582

583 **Ubiquitination and ID**

584 Beyond the well-established role of ubiquitination in synapse physiology, its dysregulation has been largely
585 linked to synaptic dysfunction and ID pathogenesis (George et al., 2018; Mabb and Ehlers, 2010; Upadhyay et
586 al., 2017). As listed in table 1, causal genes directly encode either components of the ubiquitin machinery or
587 regulators of ubiquitination (*PLAA* and *MAGEL2* genes). A third category, not discussed here for space
588 constraints comprises genes encoding targets of ubiquitination in which pathogenic mutations may change
589 their ubiquitination profile. The molecular mechanisms underlying the function of the first two categories of
590 genes and the neuronal substrates that they target are poorly characterized. For these reasons the molecular
591 pathogenesis of these forms of ID is unclear.

592 In general, ubiquitin-linked ID forms present co-morbidities that are commonly present in ID. Mental
593 impairment is often accompanied by dysmorphic features and multiple neurological and neuropsychiatric
594 manifestations (e.g. epilepsy, motor dysfunction and autistic behaviors). Many syndromes are also
595 multisystem disorders underscoring the ubiquitous importance of ubiquitination for tissue and body formation
596 and function. To the best of our knowledge, a clear classification of ID forms, and more generally of brain
597 disorders linked to defective ubiquitination does not exist. Functional and genetic groups may be however
598 elaborated. For instance, a genetic classification may be based on components of the enzymatic cascade

599 mediating the different steps of ubiquitin conjugation/deconjugation (e.g. E2, E3 and DUB enzymes).
600 Functional classes may include ubiquitinating enzymes involved in distinct cellular functions, such as
601 regulation of transcription, trafficking, cell division or proteasome activity. Though other criteria may
602 certainly be applied to propose alternative classifications including co-morbidities, no unique behavioral
603 phenotypes associate with any of the aforementioned groups. Overall, it clearly emerges that ubiquitination
604 and its delicate homeostasis are fundamental for brain physiology. Indeed, the perturbation of this equilibrium
605 due to the altered expression or activity of a single E3 ubiquitin ligase is hardly compensated by the other
606 ~600 E3 ligases and is sufficient to lead to severe pathological states of the brain. Here, we discuss in more
607 details the implications of defective ubiquitination in the molecular pathogenesis of two of the most common
608 forms of syndromic ID, the Angelman and Down syndromes.

609

610 Angelman Syndrome (AS)

611 AS (OMIM 105830) is a relatively rare neurodevelopmental disorder (prevalence of 1/15,000 live births)
612 characterized by severe intellectual deficit, motor dysfunction, unusually happy demeanor, seizures and
613 autism-like behavior (Buiting et al., 2016; Clayton-Smith, 2003; Margolis et al., 2015). AS results from
614 distinct genetic abnormalities that ultimately lead to the loss of the brain-specific imprinted *UBE3A* (ubiquitin
615 protein ligase E3A, also referred to as E6AP) gene (Mabb et al., 2011). *UBE3A* encodes three E3 ubiquitin
616 ligase isoforms that are generated by alternative splicing and localize either in the nucleus or cytosol (Miao et
617 al., 2013). In the cytosol, *UBE3A* is found in axonal terminals and dendritic spines (Burette et al., 2018;
618 Dindot et al., 2007). Whilst *UBE3A* loss results in AS, elevated expression or activity of *UBE3A* represent the
619 most identifiable genetic form of ASD, indicating that a tight balance in the dosage of this gene is critical to
620 develop functional neuronal circuits.

621 Data from AS mouse models suggests that *UBE3A* plays a key role in modulating synaptic pathways
622 important for cognition and behavior. Neurons from *ube3a*-KO mice display abnormal dendritic spines,
623 reduced excitatory neurotransmission and impaired synaptic plasticity (Avagliano Trezza et al., 2019; Dindot
624 et al., 2007; Kim et al., 2016; Pignatelli et al., 2014; J. Wang et al., 2019; Yashiro et al., 2009). Given the
625 primary function of *UBE3A* as E3 ubiquitin ligase, defective ubiquitination is thought to be at the basis of

626 neuronal dysfunctions and clinical manifestations of AS. However, only a few substrates have been identified
627 and shown to be functionally relevant to AS etiology. For these reasons, the molecular underpinnings of
628 UBE3A function remain enigmatic. Different mechanisms, mainly driven by the defective ubiquitination
629 hypothesis, have been put forward on the pathogenic role of UBE3A. (i) In physiological conditions, UBE3A
630 may indirectly modulate the number of AMPARs at the postsynaptic membrane by ubiquitinating the
631 aforementioned signaling protein Arc and promoting its degradation (Greer et al., 2010). Therefore, loss of
632 UBE3A may increase Arc levels and lead to enhanced AMPAR internalization and ultimately, depression of
633 glutamatergic transmission. (ii) A second synaptic substrate of UBE3A is ephexin 5 (Margolis et al., 2010).
634 Ephexin 5 is a guanine nucleotide exchange factor (GEF) activator of the RhoA GTPase that limits the number
635 of excitatory synapses via inhibition of the synaptogenic, *trans*-synaptic EphB receptor/ephrin ligand complex
636 (Henderson and Dalva, 2018). *ube3a*-KO mice display increased amounts of ephexin 5 and abnormal density
637 of excitatory synapses, indicating that UBE3A-dependent degradation of ephexin 5 is critical for the normal
638 development of excitatory synapses. (iii) A recent study suggested that UBE3A ubiquitinates the small
639 conductance potassium channel SK2, whose major function is to repolarize neuronal membranes after
640 depolarization (Ngo-Anh et al., 2005), and facilitates its endocytosis (Sun et al., 2015b). In line with defective
641 ubiquitination of SK2, its surface expression is significantly increased in *ube3a*-KO mice, resulting in
642 membrane hyperpolarization and impaired synaptic plasticity. (iv) A role for CaMKII was proposed based on
643 the observation that hippocampi derived from AS mice display reduced CaMKII activity and excessive
644 inhibitory autophosphorylation (Weeber et al., 2003). In particular, the correction of some AS neurological
645 deficits obtained preventing CaMKII inhibitory autophosphorylation suggests that CaMKII may be
646 instrumental to UBE3A-dependent pathways underlying AS phenotype (van Woerden et al., 2007). However,
647 it is not known whether UBE3A directly targets CaMKII for degradation or targets unknown kinases or
648 phosphatases that in turn modulate CaMKII phosphorylation. Strikingly, PTPA, which is the activator of a
649 major phosphatase of CaMKII, PP2A, was recently identified as UBE3A target (J. Wang et al., 2019).
650 However, the modulation of PTPA levels does not affect the phosphorylation of CaMKII, suggesting other
651 downstream substrates. (v) In cerebellar Purkinje cells of AS mice, mTOR (mechanistic target of rapamycin)
652 signaling is unbalanced, resulting in up-regulated mTORC1 and reduced mTORC2 (Sun et al., 2015a).

653 mTORC1 activation relies on its lysosomal recruitment through the interaction with the Rag GTPase-
654 Regulator complex. UBE3A ubiquitinates the p18 subunit of the Regulator complex. Therefore, in AS mice
655 defective p18 ubiquitination enhances mTORC1 activity by increasing its lysosomal recruitment. (vi) A recent
656 proteomic-based study aimed at identifying new UBE3A substrates implicated autophagy in AS pathogenesis
657 (T. Wang et al., 2019). UBE3A physically associates with and ubiquitinates the autophagy regulator
658 Huntington-associated protein 1 (HAP1), a key protein for autophagosome trafficking. In AS mouse model,
659 increased HAP1 leads to excessive autophagy and ultimately, dendritic spine defects. Consistently,
660 pharmacological attenuation of autophagy partially alleviates synaptic dysfunction and behavioral deficits in
661 AS mice.

662 The above studies have focused on mechanisms underlying weakened excitatory synapses. However, the vast
663 majority of AS patients display autistic behavior and seizure susceptibility (Clayton-Smith, 2003), suggesting
664 that loss of UBE3A may increase the excitation (E)/inhibition (I) ratio in the neocortex. Recent evidence
665 proposed that UBE3A loss might impact GABAergic neurons more severely than the excitatory counterpart,
666 with the potential net outcome favoring hyperexcitability (Judson et al., 2016; Wallace et al., 2012). Future
667 studies aimed at investigating whether UBE3A directly operates at inhibitory synapses and which are its
668 substrates will help clarifying UBE3A-mediated mechanisms modulating neuronal excitability.

669 Together, these studies clearly indicate that UBE3A regulates several cellular pathways that critically
670 contribute to synapse development and function, and that altered ubiquitination is central to AS etiology.
671 Though the number of identified UBE3A substrates is rapidly increasing, the functional relevance of these
672 interactions is not clear yet and an integrated picture of UBE3A function is lacking. In addition, the weight of
673 individual substrates and pathways in the pathogenesis of AS and its clinical manifestations is still enigmatic.

674

675 Down Syndrome (DS)

676 DS (OMIM 190685) is the most common cause of ID and accounts for ~15-20% of all individuals affected by
677 ID. DS is a complex genetic disorder characterized by heterogenous clinical manifestations. Among them,
678 cognitive impairment is present in all DS individuals (Antonarakis et al., 2004). The DS critical region
679 (DSCR) is a relatively small locus on chr. 21, and its triplication is necessary and sufficient to generate DS

680 cognitive deficits. One of the genes localized in the DSCR is *TTC3*, which is consistently up-regulated in
681 patients and animal models of DS (Saran et al., 2003). *TTC3* encodes an E3 ubiquitin ligase that targets a
682 phosphorylated form of the kinase Akt (Suizu et al., 2009), which is critical for several cellular functions in
683 the brain (Hers et al., 2011). In *Ts65Dn* mice, the most common animal model of DS, the abnormal levels of
684 *TTC3* enhance ubiquitination and degradation of Akt. Among its multiple synaptic functions, Akt
685 phosphorylates the β subunits of GABA_ARs in hippocampal neurons, thereby increasing the number of surface
686 GABA_ARs at inhibitory synapses (Wang et al., 2003). Remarkably, DS individuals show a higher incidence of
687 seizures, raising the possibility that enhanced *TTC3*-mediated degradation of Akt leads to the loss of E/I
688 equilibrium in the brain and hyperexcitability. In developing neurons, *TTC3* overexpression also limits neurite
689 outgrowth and modifies the morphology of the Golgi apparatus through the modulation of actin-regulating
690 pathways (Berto et al., 2014). Strikingly, *TTC3* also significantly correlates with other DS-unrelated brain
691 pathologies associated with ID, suggesting an essential role for *TTC3* in complex cognitive functions
692 (Vilardell et al., 2011).

693 Dysfunctions of global neuronal ubiquitome in DS are also detected in aged *Ts65Dn* mice and postmortem
694 brains of DS patients. Such alterations are linked to the accumulation of inclusion bodies in the cerebellum, a
695 cellular hallmark of Alzheimer's disease (AD), a neurodegenerative disorder that is particularly frequent in DS
696 (Necchi et al., 2011; Tramutola et al., 2017). On the other hand, it was reported that in both DS patients and
697 *Ts65Dn* mice the *USP16* gene, which maps on chr.21 and codes for a deubiquitinase, is critical to DS
698 pathogenesis (Adorno et al., 2013). *USP16* triplication excessively removes ubiquitin from histone H2A, a key
699 event for the self-renewal and expansion of different progenitor cells, including neuronal progenitors. In line
700 with this, a reduced expansion of postnatal neuronal progenitors is observed in DS patients.

701 All of these pieces of evidence suggest that unbalanced ubiquitination critically contributes to neuronal circuit
702 dysregulation and clinical manifestations of DS, including ID. The relative contribution of these pathways to
703 the molecular pathogenesis of DS remains largely unknown.

704

705 **Sumoylation and ID**

706 As aforementioned, sumoylation is critical to build up proper synaptic connections by modulating the function
707 of several neuronal proteins. The evidence that several SUMO targets are ID-associated proteins raises the
708 possibility that impaired sumoylation may be relevant to ID etiology. An increasing number of molecular
709 studies now supports this hypothesis and suggests that dysregulated neuronal sumoylation may participate to
710 the development of two common syndromic forms of ID, the RTT and DS. Furthermore, defective
711 sumoylation may potentially be implicated in other ID forms, such as FXS, Phelan-McDermid syndrome
712 (PMS) and the Cc2d1-dependent non-syndromic ID.

713

714 Rett syndrome (RTT)

715 RTT (OMIM 312750) is a devastating neurodevelopmental disorder and the leading cause of genetic ID in
716 young girls. Almost 95% of RTT individuals carry mutations in the *MECP2* gene. As described above,
717 MeCP2 is sumoylated at K223 and K412 residues and these modifications regulate the activity of MeCP2 as
718 transcriptional repressor. The analysis of sumoylation profiles of seven different mutated MeCP2 variants
719 identified in RTT patients reveals that six of these mutations decrease MeCP2 sumoylation due to a lower
720 affinity for the SUMO E3 ligase PIAS1 (Tai et al., 2016). Strikingly, while the lentiviral expression of either
721 WT or sumoylated MeCP2 in conditional *Mecp2*-KO mice restores some cellular and behavioral deficits, such
722 as social interaction, fear memory and LTP, the expression of a non-sumoylatable MeCP2 mutant fails to
723 rescue these phenotypes. In this study, it was also demonstrated that these pathological mutations are
724 associated with altered MeCP2 phosphorylation at S421, a PTM that is known to promote its sumoylation. In
725 the same study, the authors also demonstrated that mice expressing non-sumoylatable MeCP2 display 12-fold
726 decrease in *Wnt6* mRNA levels compared to WT animals. Very recently, the same group showed that lentiviral
727 expression of *Wnt6* rescues defective MeCP2 sumoylation in MeCP2 T158A mouse model of RTT.
728 Importantly, *Wnt6* transduction and enhanced MeCP2 sumoylation also resulted in partial amelioration of
729 locomotor and social behavioral deficits (Hsu et al., 2020). Together, these pioneer studies provided for the
730 first time a link between altered sumoylation and the etiology of ID, representing an important milestone in the
731 field.

732

733 ID linked to SUMO machinery-encoding genes

734 Since the *SUMO3* paralogue gene is located in the long arm of chr. 21, the excessive dosage of *SUMO3* is an
735 intriguing hypothesis in DS pathogenesis. Several transcriptional factors and the glucocorticoid receptor,
736 which are known to control cognitive functions, are targeted by SUMO3 (Schorova and Martin, 2016). In line
737 with this, the levels of free and conjugated SUMO2/3 proteins are significantly higher in hippocampal lysates
738 derived from DS patients compared to healthy individuals (Gardiner, 2006). Yet, a comprehensive view of
739 SUMO3 neuronal targets is lacking and the impact of SUMO3 triplication on DS etiology remains elusive.
740 Recently, Binda and colleagues reported a marked decrease of the SUMO2/3-specific deconjugating enzyme
741 SENP3 in DS patients without any corresponding increase of SUMO2/3-conjugated proteins (Binda et al.,
742 2017). Future studies aiming at systematically analyzing SUMO3 substrates in the brain will be of invaluable
743 help to elucidate the role of enhanced sumoylation in DS pathogenesis.

744 A woman with profound developmental delay associated with several other clinical manifestations was found
745 to carry a microdeletion in the chr. 19 that resulted in the haploinsufficiency of 15 genes including *SAE1*, a
746 subunit of the SUMO1 activating enzyme (Leal et al., 2009). Though the authors suggested that the loss of
747 *SAE1* gene may correlate with an impaired development of the cleft lip and palate, it remains to be determined
748 whether this alteration might also participate to other pathological features, comprising defective cognitive
749 functions.

750 *ZMIZ1* gene codes for an androgen receptor coactivator that functions as an E3 SUMO ligase (Sharma, 2003)
751 and recently identified mutations were associated with ID and developmental delay (Carapito et al., 2019).
752 Notably, all identified *ZMIZ1* mutations occur in the SUMO acceptor site, suggesting that they might
753 compromise the E3 SUMO ligase activity of *ZMIZ1*, resulting in a failure of sumoylation homeostasis in
754 neurons.

755

756 *Cc2d1-dependent non-syndromic ID*

757 Mutations in the Coiled-coil and C2 domain containing 1A (*CC2D1A*) gene are associated with non-
758 syndromic ID (OMIM 608443). This gene codes for CC2D1A, a DNA binding protein that regulates multiple
759 cellular signaling pathways, including serotonin and dopamine receptors, dendritic arborization, synapse

760 maturation and plasticity (Al-Tawashi et al., 2012; Manzini et al., 2014; Oaks et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019;
761 Zhao et al., 2011). Consistent with these roles, the loss of CC2D1A *in vivo* determines the appearance of
762 cognitive and social deficits (Oaks et al., 2017). Very recently, it was shown that conditional deletion of
763 *cc2d1a* in excitatory neurons of the forebrain leads to decreased levels of SENP1 and SENP3. As a
764 consequence, the desumoylation of the small GTPase Rac1, one of the major targets of SENP1 and SENP3, is
765 suppressed (Yang et al., 2019). Since Rac1 activity is enhanced by sumoylation, hyperactivated Rac1 results in
766 abnormal dendritic morphology and synaptic dysfunction. Remarkably, pharmacological blockade of Rac1
767 activity partially rescues deficits in synaptic plasticity and memory observed in *cc2d1a*-cKO mice (Yang et al.,
768 2019). In conclusion, this work provides further experimental evidence supporting the hypothesis that aberrant
769 sumoylation is a key molecular determinant underlying ID etiology.

770

771 *mGlu5R-related IDs: PMS and FXS*

772 Phelan-McDermid syndrome (PMS) and FXS are two major forms of ID and are associated with dysregulation
773 of the mGlu5R-dependent pathway. The loss of *SHANK3* gene, which is caused by deletions of the terminal
774 end of chr. 22 long arm, is critical to PMS development. Shank3 is a major scaffolding protein of excitatory
775 synapses that anchors, together with Homer1, mGlu5Rs to the postsynaptic membrane. As a consequence, the
776 loss of Shank3 impairs mGlu5R activity by destabilizing the pool of surface receptors (Vicidomini et al.,
777 2017). Conversely, FXS mouse models carrying loss-of-function mutations of *Fmr1* gene are characterized by
778 excessive mGlu5R-dependent signaling (Prieto et al., 2019).

779 Considering the functional relevance of mGlu5R to SUMO homeostasis (Loriol et al., 2014; Schorova et al.,
780 2019), the analysis of brain sumoylome in animal models of PMS and FXS is of primary importance and
781 might uncover pivotal roles of sumoylation in the molecular pathogenesis of these neurodevelopmental
782 disorders. Recently, new evidence further supported the possibility that sumoylation might be a key
783 determinant in the pathogenesis of FXS (Khayachi et al., 2018; Prieto et al., 2019). The novel pathological
784 missense mutation R138Q of *FMRI* gene was identified in three unrelated individuals presenting
785 developmental delays, ID and seizures (Collins et al., 2010; Diaz et al., 2018; Sitzmann et al., 2018). In
786 contrast to other FXS cases, this mutation does not affect the expression levels of FMRP protein. As the

787 R138Q mutation localizes in close proximity to the SUMO site K130 of FMRP, it is possible that the R138Q
788 mutation causes aberrant FMRP sumoylation and this impairment may be causative of FXS. Similarly, the
789 F126S mutation, which was reported in a FXS male patient presenting ID and autistic features (Quartier et al.,
790 2017), also localizes nearby K130 residue. As this mutation replaces a phenylalanine (F) with an S residue, it
791 likely generates a novel phosphorylation site, which could subsequently promote sumoylation at K130 (Loriol
792 et al., 2014). Further studies are required to better explore this hypothesis.

793

794 **FUNCTIONAL INTERPLAY BETWEEN UBIQUITINATION AND UBLs**

795 Recently, the existence of a dynamic interplay between ubiquitination and UBLs provided an intriguing
796 perspective that could lead to the identification of novel principles underlying synapse development and
797 function. As mentioned above, the best characterized function of Nedd8 is to enhance the activity of Cullin E3
798 ligases providing evidence of a direct interaction with ubiquitination (Enchev et al., 2015). Moreover,
799 neddylation-dependent ubiquitination and degradation of DNMT3a1 is critical to increase BDNF expression
800 and is required to memory consolidation in the hippocampus (Bayraktar et al., 2019). PSD95 is targeted by the
801 E3 ligase Mdm2, which mediates both ubiquitination and neddylation (Bianchetta et al., 2011; Colledge et al.,
802 2003; Vogl et al., 2015). However, neddylation does not change PSD95 degradation rate (Vogl et al., 2015)
803 and the possible crosstalk between these two PTMs on PSD95 remains unknown. Altogether, more study is
804 needed to better understand neddylation and its interplay with other PTMs.

805 Emerging evidence also indicates that ubiquitination and sumoylation reciprocally interact to precisely
806 regulate protein function. Numerous neuronal substrates are targeted by both ubiquitin and SUMO
807 machineries. Proteomic approaches showed that ~25% of SUMO-acceptor K residues are also ubiquitinated,
808 suggesting that these two pathways likely compete with each other for the same K residues (Tammsalu et al.,
809 2014). However, a few examples suggest that this interplay is not only antagonistic, but ubiquitination and
810 sumoylation can also operate in synergy. The hypoxia-inducible factor 1 alpha (HIF1 α) requires to be
811 sumoylated for its subsequent UPS-dependent degradation (Cheng et al., 2007). Similarly, the sequential
812 sumoylation and ubiquitination of the serine hydroxymethyltransferase 1 (SHMT1) and the regulatory subunit
813 of the kinase IKK are required to control the rate of nuclear import/export of these proteins and, ultimately, to

814 regulate their activity (Anderson et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2003). Moreover, the impairment of
815 ubiquitination/sumoylation crosstalk critically contributes to the development of neurodegenerative disorders.
816 For instance, in AD, this interplay is critical for the formation of tau-containing neurofibrillary tangles, a
817 primary hallmark of AD. Indeed, hyperphosphorylation of tau protein enhances its sumoylation in a β -
818 Amyloid (A β)-dependent manner. Once sumoylated, tau is less ubiquitinated and degraded, favoring tau
819 aggregation and decreasing its solubility (Luo et al., 2014). Another neurodegenerative disorder in which the
820 competition between ubiquitination and sumoylation is relevant for disease pathogenesis is Huntington's
821 disease (HD). HD is caused by the expansion of huntingtin (HTT) polyglutamine repeats. Proteolytic cleavage
822 of mutated HTT generates a pathogenic fragment (Httex1p) that creates toxic aggregates in the nucleus and
823 cytoplasm. Both ubiquitination and sumoylation target K6 and K9 of the Httex1p fragment and mediate
824 opposite effects. Sumoylation increases Httex1p stability and aggregation, its function as transcriptional
825 repressor and ultimately, its neurotoxicity (Steffan et al., 2004). Conversely, ubiquitination reduces Httex1p
826 neurotoxicity probably by promoting its degradation (Kalchman et al., 1996). Consistent with this, in a
827 *Drosophila* model of HD, sumoylation and ubiquitination of Httex1p worsen and abrogate neurodegeneration,
828 respectively (Steffan et al., 2004).

829 To date, the functional interplay between ubiquitination and sumoylation in ID pathogenesis has been poorly
830 characterized. Growing evidence suggests that a defective crosstalk might underlie, at least partially, synaptic
831 dysfunction observed in certain forms of ID. As described above, *SUMO3*, the E3 ubiquitin ligase *TTC3* and
832 the deubiquinating enzyme *USP16* are located within the DSCR and are triplicated in DS individuals (Adorno
833 et al., 2013; Gardiner, 2006; Saran et al., 2003). The hyperabundance of *SUMO3* could either decrease the
834 ubiquitination of those substrates for which ubiquitination and sumoylation compete or enhance the
835 ubiquitination of those targets for which the two PTMs operate in synergy. Triplication of *TTC3* may also lead
836 to an unbalanced ubiquitination/sumoylation that selectively involves *TTC3* substrates. For instance, Akt, a
837 major target of *TTC3*, is also a known *SUMO* target, raising the possibility that enhanced Akt ubiquitination
838 impairs its sumoylation status in DS patients. Whether other *TTC3* substrates are subjected to the same
839 regulatory mechanism is not known as the majority of *TTC3* targets are not identified yet. Thus, besides
840 assessing the level of Akt sumoylation in DS, it is of great interest to identify novel *TTC3* substrates and

841 investigate whether they are also targeted by sumoylation. A second ID form in which unbalanced
842 ubiquitination/sumoylation could potentially play a central role is FXS. As mentioned above, novel
843 pathological missense point mutations in the *FRMI* gene are closely located to the SUMO site K130 and likely
844 interfere with FMRP sumoylation (Khayachi et al., 2018; Prieto et al., 2019). Furthermore, FMRP is also
845 subjected to activity-dependent ubiquitination by the APC/C complex (Hou et al., 2006; Huang et al., 2015). If
846 ubiquitin and SUMO machineries competed for the same K residues in FMRP sequence, defective
847 sumoylation may promote its ubiquitination. Alternatively, if sumoylation, which is required to release FMRP
848 from dendritic mRNA granules (Khayachi et al., 2018), is instrumental to subsequent ubiquitination, these
849 mutations may affect FMRP degradation, resulting in reduced local translation. Finally, it is also tempting to
850 consider this possibility in regard to the AS. Indeed, Arc, a major synaptic substrate of UBE3A, is also
851 subjected to sumoylation (Nair et al., 2017). Together, the involvement of an unbalanced crosstalk between
852 ubiquitination and sumoylation in synaptic dysfunction of ID is an exciting hypothesis and, if confirmed by
853 further experimental data, it would define novel principles underlying the molecular logistics of synapse
854 physiology and the pathogenesis of a spectrum of neurodevelopmental and psychiatric disorders.

855

856 **CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES**

857 As summarized in this review, a wealth of studies clearly demonstrated pivotal roles for ubiquitination and
858 UBLs in the assembly and refinement of neuronal circuits, maintenance of neuronal homeostasis and the
859 emergence of complex cognitive functions. The fine spatiotemporal regulation of these PTMs is of primary
860 importance during brain formation, a process that is characterized by intense synaptic plasticity and, on the
861 other end, by high susceptibility to toxic insults. Therefore, genetic or environmental challenges to
862 ubiquitination and sumoylation pathways critically contribute to the etiology of synaptopathies, including ID.
863 Concerning neddylation, though it might be involved in ID, no evidence is currently available to support this
864 hypothesis. Nevertheless, the molecular mechanisms that underpin impaired ubiquitination and sumoylation in
865 ID are unclear as well as a comprehensive view of neuronal ubiquitome and sumoylome is lacking. Here, we
866 provide a few outlooks that are crucial to better understand the role of these two regulatory systems in the
867 brain.

868 A major limitation to advance our knowledge on the pathophysiological role of ubiquitination and UBLs
869 concerns the technical challenges to detect endogenous substrates. These modifications are transient and
870 restricted to specific subcellular compartments, developmental stages and states of neuronal activity. This
871 results in scarcely abundant steady-state levels of modified targets. In recent years, new MS-based strategies
872 were developed to efficiently capture ubiquitinated, sumoylated and neddylated proteins in native tissues. For
873 example, ubiquitomes and sumoylomes may be enriched using a novel monoclonal antibody that recognizes a
874 diglycine tag on K residues of trypsinized peptides that is present on ubiquitinated and sumoylated proteins
875 solely (Na et al., 2012; Tammsalu et al., 2015). This technique was recently combined with CRISPR-Cas9
876 genome editing of *NEDD8* gene to reveal the neddylome in HEK cells (Vogl et al., 2020). Alternatively, the *in*
877 *vivo* proximity-dependent biotin identification (iBioID) approach may efficiently detect substrates of specific
878 ubiquitin and UBL machineries (Coyaud et al., 2015; Pirone et al., 2017).

879 A fertile area of future research will be the investigation of environmental risk factors for ID that might affect
880 neuronal ubiquitination and UBLs. As previously mentioned, ID-linked environmental factors comprise
881 alcohol and drug abuse and infections during pregnancy, birth complication and severe malnutrition. For
882 instance, prenatal exposure to one of the most commonly used anticonvulsant drugs, the valproic acid, is
883 associated with an increased risk of autism (Christensen et al., 2013) and a few reports suggest that it may
884 regulate the UPS (Kwon et al., 2013). Microarray transcript and proteome profiling of mouse models of Fetal
885 Alcohol Syndrome Disorders (FASD) revealed a significant down-regulation of the proteasomal function
886 (Green et al., 2007; Mason et al., 2012). In particular, the E2 conjugating enzyme UBE2N, which is known to
887 be critical for neurodevelopment (Muralidhar and Thomas, 1993), is among the identified proteins. Similarly,
888 fetal cortices exposed to alcohol display an increased sumoylation of the Heat shock protein 1 (HSP1), a
889 fundamental cellular sensor of environmental proteotoxic stress, resulting in prolonged activation of HSP1 (El
890 Fatimy et al., 2014). The E3 SUMO ligase PIASy is up-regulated in alcohol-treated cultured cells and drives
891 the induction of autophagy (Ran et al., 2018), a well-known mechanism involved in synapse assembly and
892 maturation (Tomoda et al., 2020). Yet, whether alcohol-dependent PIASy up-regulation could contribute to the
893 synaptic dysfunction in FASD is not known. Perinatal asphyxia (PA) is an obstetric complication derived from
894 impaired gas exchange that inevitably leads to aberrant synaptic networks and severe clinical manifestations,

895 such as epilepsy, schizophrenia and ID. A number of studies reported enhanced ubiquitination levels in striatal
896 and hippocampal synapses of PA animal models (Capani et al., 2009; Saraceno et al., 2012). Furthermore,
897 hypoxia triggers sumoylation of Nav1.2 channels (Plant et al., 2016), which provides the earliest neuronal
898 response to hypoxia and is a major determinant of hypoxia-induced neuronal death (Weber and Taylor, 1994).
899 Since TTX-induced inhibition of sodium currents prevents neuronal death in acute hypoxia (Taylor et al.,
900 1995), modulation of Nav1.2 sumoylation might represent a novel target to develop neuroprotective therapies
901 (Plant et al., 2016). Finally, nicotine administration at concentrations achieved by smokers inhibits the UPS in
902 the prefrontal cortex of adult mice and influences synaptic plasticity by regulating the levels of multiple PSD
903 proteins, including scaffolding molecules and receptors (Rezvani et al., 2012, 2007). However, the direct
904 effect of smoking during pregnancy on the synaptic ubiquitome of the fetal brain remains elusive. Altogether,
905 these examples support the hypothesis that ID-linked environmental risk factors affect ubiquitin and UBLs
906 pathways, which in turn may contribute to ID pathogenesis. As these factors typically alter multiple cellular
907 pathways, it would be of great interest to dissect the weight of defective ubiquitination and UBLs to ID onset.
908 At present, no effective medical therapies are available to treat ID. Defining the roles of ubiquitination and
909 UBL modifications and the molecular mechanisms underlying these pathways in physiological and
910 pathological conditions could open new venues to identify novel therapeutic strategies. Given that
911 ubiquitination and UBLs virtually regulate all cellular processes, they are attractive drug targets. For example,
912 compounds that modulate ubiquitination, sumoylation and neddylation have been tested to treat cancer and
913 other pathologies (Bernstock et al., 2018; Landré et al., 2014; Nawrocki et al., 2012). However, the majority of
914 the molecules that are currently being tested activates or inhibits global cellular ubiquitination or UBL
915 modifications, thus inevitably leading to relevant side effects. Therefore, the development of new compounds
916 that precisely modulate individual components or branches of ubiquitin and UBL systems and their interaction
917 with specific substrates is urgently needed. Finally, a better elucidation of synaptic ubiquitination and UBL
918 pathways will be of invaluable help to move towards precision medicine.

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1622 **LEGENDS**

1623 **Figure 1. Neuronal ubiquitination and ubiquitin-like modifications.** (A, C) Major components of
1624 excitatory and inhibitory synapses targeted by ubiquitin (blue squares) SUMO (purple triangles) and Nedd8
1625 (orange hexagons) pathways. Deubiquitinating enzymes (green clamshell-like shapes) and components of the
1626 SUMO (Ubc9 and SENPs) and Nedd8 machineries (NAE, UBC12 and UBE2F) are also indicated. Though
1627 Nedd8 pathway and targets are also present in the presynaptic compartment, for simplicity they are depicted in
1628 the postsynaptic region only. In (A) E3 ubiquitin ligases operating at excitatory synapses and their known
1629 substrates are listed in the left table. (B) Nuclear sumoylation and neddylation critical to synaptic function are
1630 indicated.

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1632 **Figure 2. Postsynaptic control of glutamate and GABA_A receptors by ubiquitination and sumoylation.**

1633 UPS-dependent degradation (green arrows) of PSD-95 destabilizes surface AMPARs, resulting in enhanced
1634 receptor lateral mobility and consequently, endocytosis (box A). Ubiquitination of GluA1 and GluA2
1635 decreases surface AMPARs through clathrin-dependent endocytosis (orange arrows). Ubiquitinated Arc is
1636 degraded via the UPS pathway. As Arc is a major regulator of AMPAR internalization, reduced Arc levels
1637 suppress AMPAR endocytosis. Conversely, sumoylated Arc triggers AMPAR internalization. Moreover,
1638 ubiquitination of intracellular GluA1-4 may also promote AMPAR sorting to the lysosomal degradation
1639 pathway (red arrows). Ubiquitination of mGlu1-5 receptors enhanced their clathrin-dependent endocytosis.
1640 Surface NMDARs are regulated by the ubiquitination pathway in a subunit-dependent manner. GluN2B
1641 undergoes a phosphorylation-dependent ubiquitination (box B), leading to UPS-dependent degradation of
1642 NMDARs. GluN2D ubiquitination enhances its degradation, though it is not clear whether it utilizes UPS- or
1643 lysosomal-dependent pathways (green and red dotted arrows). Finally, ubiquitination of newly synthesized
1644 GluN1 and GluN2A results in NMDAR retrotranslocation from the ER to the cytosol and subsequent
1645 degradation through the ER-associated degradation (ERAD) pathway (blue arrows). Similar to GluN2D,
1646 GluK2 ubiquitination is phosphorylation-dependent and triggers its degradation through an as yet ill-defined
1647 pathway (green and red dotted arrows). In contrast, sumoylated GluK2-containing KARs are removed from
1648 the synaptic membrane via clathrin-dependent endocytosis. At inhibitory synapses, ubiquitinated γ 2-

1649 containing GABA_AR are sorted to the lysosomal degradation pathway, while β3-containing GABA_AR are
1650 ubiquitinated in the ER and degraded through the ERAD machinery.

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GENE	PROTEIN	DISEASE	GENETIC ABNORMALITIES	REFERENCES
<i>ASXL3</i>	component of the Polycomb repressive deubiquitination (PR-DUB) complex	Bainbridge–Ropers syndrome, BRS (OMIM 615485) and ASD	<i>de novo</i> truncating mutations in BRS and missense mutations in ASD	(Bainbridge et al., 2013; De Rubeis et al., 2014)
<i>CUL4B</i>	scaffolding protein stabilizing cullin RING E3 ligase	XLID (OMIM 300304)	missense mutations	(Wang et al., 2013; Zou et al., 2007)
<i>HECW2</i>	E3 ubiquitin ligase HECW2	Neurodevelopmental disorder with hypotonia, seizures and absent language, NDHSAL (OMIM 617268)	missense mutations	(Halvardson et al., 2016)
<i>HERC1</i>	E3 ubiquitin ligase HERC1	Macrocephaly, dysmorphic facies, and psychomotor retardation, MDFPMR (OMIM 617011)	missense and frameshift mutations	(Aggarwal et al., 2016; Nguyen et al., 2016; Ortega-Recalde et al., 2015)
<i>HERC2</i>	E3 ubiquitin ligase HERC2	Syndrome of intellectual disability, autism and variable neurological deficits (OMIM 615516)	missense mutations	(Puffenberger et al., 2012)
<i>HUWE1</i>	HECT, UBA and WWE domain containing 1, E3 ubiquitin protein ligase	Turner type, XLID (OMIM 309590)	microduplications, missense mutations	(Froyen et al., 2008; Moortgat et al., 2018)
<i>MAGEL2</i>	E3 ubiquitin ligase enhancer	Prader-Willi syndrome, PWS (OMIM 176270) and Schaaf-Yang syndrome, SHFYNG (OMIM 615547)	interstitial deletions and maternal uniparental disomy in PWS; truncating mutations in SHFYNG	(Tacer and Potts, 2017)
<i>MID2</i>	member of the TRIPartite Motif (TRIM) family of RING E3 ligases	XLID (OMIM 300928)	missense mutation	(Geetha et al., 2014)
<i>OTUD6B</i>	member of the ovarian tumor domain (OTU)-containing subfamily of deubiquitinating enzymes	Intellectual developmental disorder with dysmorphic facies, seizures, and distal limb anomalies, IDDFS (OMIM 617452)	truncating and missense mutations	(Santiago-Sim et al., 2017)
<i>PLAA</i>	Ubiquitin binding protein Phospholipase A2 Activating Protein	Neurodevelopmental disorder with progressive microcephaly, spasticity, and brain anomalies, NDMSBA (OMIM 617527)	missense mutations	(Falik Zaccai et al., 2017; Hall et al., 2017)
<i>RLIM</i>	RNF12 E3 ubiquitin ligase	Tonne-Kalscheuer syndrome, XLID (OMIM 300978)	missense mutation	(Tønne et al., 2015)
<i>TRIM50</i>	member of the TRIPartite Motif (TRIM) family of RING E3 ligases	William-Beuren syndrome, WBS (OMIM 194050)	microdeletion on chr. 7q11.23	(Micale et al., 2008)
<i>TRIP12</i>	member of the HECT domain E3 ubiquitin ligases family	Intellectual disability with or without ASD (OMIM 6177520)	CNVs, missense, frameshift, splicing mutations	(Zhang et al., 2017)
<i>UBE2A</i>	E2 ubiquitin conjugating enzyme E2A	XLID type Nascimento (OMIM 300860)	truncating and missense mutations	(Budny et al., 2010; Nascimento et al., 2006)
<i>UBE3B</i>	E3 ubiquitin ligase E3B	Blepharophimosis-ptosis-intellectual disability syndrome, BPIDS (OMIM 244450)	truncating mutations	(Basel-Vanagaite et al., 2012)
<i>USPX9</i>	Deubiquitinating enzyme FAF-X	Female-restricted X-linked non-syndromic mental retardation-99 (OMIM 300919)	truncating mutation and X-chr. deletion	(Au et al., 2017)

